

THE USE OF SOCIOLOGICAL RESEARCH RESULTS IN PRACTICE

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Abstract: Sociological research is a system of logically consistent methodological, methodological and organizational procedures subject to a single goal: to obtain accurate and objective information about the social object, phenomenon and process under study. Sociological research should be based on the use of specific scientific methods, techniques and procedures specific to sociology. In order to clearly and clearly understand the essence of the sociological research process, it is necessary to understand the system and essence of the concepts most used in the sociological research process.

Keywords: research, reporting, Research Program, research results, software.

Each sociological study conducted is analyzed and summarized. It is convenient to process the results of the survey and make statistical calculations, but the results that have been processed, as the opponents of this method say, seem correct. In addition, cases of dizziness from responding are common, especially when questionnaires are sent by mail. The language used in interpreting the conditions and results of the survey is often very far from the real living individuals responding. It is difficult to even imagine the person being asked when the questions are sent by mail.

In general, the more direct and direct communication between researchers and respondents, the more informative and justified the conclusions will be. The results of the survey should be filled with materials that are as deepened as possible.

The collected material must be analyzed and coordinated to the study with the problem of four. It is not easy to process the information obtained and adapt it to the topic of research. Even, when there is an opportunity to get clear answers to all questions, Ham many studies are caught up. After analyzing the results of the study

sung, the report must be prepared. Usually published in the form of a journal article or book, the report will consist of an explanation of the nature of the research and the justification of the conclusions made. This is the final stage. Many reports result from unanswered questions and require further research.

One of the most important problems that arise in the study of problems related to research in research methodology is the assumption of causes and consequences. A causal connection of two events or states is a connection such that one event or state induces another.

Introduction - to the sphere of production or consumption of a scientific product that directly or indirectly provides a technical and economic effect. The scientific product is issued to the customer or consumer in the form of reports, instructions, methodology, interim instructions, technical conditions, technical project, etc. In many sectors of the economy, it is used to improve or create a new one to ensure the competitiveness of an existing product. In this case, the introduction process is introduced in two stages: the first stage – experimental-introduction to production, the second stage – serial. At the first stage, prepared experimental samples of structures, machines, materials, etc. are diligently studied under the planned different production conditions, as well as under the influence of random natural factors. Particular attention is paid to the indicators of exploitation and costs, reliability and long duration, the technicality of preparation and exploitation, environmental and anthropotechnical indicators, etc.

An explanatory note is prepared with various documents on the results of the experiment-production. In these, experimental samples are assessed on structural, technological, operational, economic, environmental, ergonomic, medico-hygienic, fireproof and other characteristics.

The first stage of implementation requires large financial costs. Because the preparation of an experimental sample is labor-intensive, and often the correction is forced to make changes again. The new product sample will be introduced into the production of the series in the second stage after an experimental production test. In this case, the size of the introduction is determined by the customer based on the

demand of the haridor market. To speed up the introduction of a scientific product, the research organization will merge with the design organization. In this situation, all work is headed by one center.

As a result, the introduction period is reduced, the quality and competitiveness of the product increases. In developed countries, this problem is solved with the help of technoparks. Technopark is an organization (legal entity) that has a close connection with one or more scientific research works, is engaged in the development of a scientific and informational environment, creates a base for mastering the production base of scientific products for the rapid penetration of scientific products into the market of new technologies. In the early 90s of the 20th century, about 340 technoparks were formed in the world.

Fundamental theoretical studies are difficult to assess with quantitative indicators of effectiveness. They usually begin to bear fruit much later after the start of work. In addition, their result is used in various sectors of the economy. Therefore, it is difficult to assess the expected effect. For such research, as a rule, quality criteria are established: the novelty of the phenomenon, the prestige of the country's science, the widespread recognition of work internationally, the contribution to the country's defense capabilities: monographs and the use of the work of their scientists in different countries, etc. Applied-scientific research and experimental design developments are evaluated by various quantitative criteria, the main of which is economic efficiency. It depends on the cost of introduction, the scale of introduction, duration and other factors.

The effectiveness of the work of a scientific employee is assessed by the novelty of the development, the number of published articles, the receipt of extracts from work, etc. The novelty criterion is the amount of an autorun certificate and patents, the receipt of an extract(excerpt) — The number of references to the work of a researcher. Economic assessment, on the other hand, is rarely used. The research group (or organization) is assessed on labor efficiency according to the following criteria: labor efficiency, the amount of topics introduced, the economic effect from

the implementation of the scientific product, the number of carryover certificates and patents received, the number of licenses sold, etc.

The effectiveness of scientific research is the basis of the strategy and tactics of creating a scientific and technical product aimed at engaging in scientific creativity and improving the well – being of the personality society. The calculation of the economic effect of scientific research is carried out in accordance with the stages of their implementation. In this regard, reasonable, expected and real economic efficiency are distinguished from each other. The objective economic effect is established in the justification of the work of scientific research and its inclusion in the work plan. In this case, the calculations are carried out approximately, taking into account the scale of the predicted introduction, according to the largest indicators. Expected economic efficiency is calculated in the process of performing scientific research. It is predicted for a specific year to be introduced into the production of scientific products. Expected efficiency is a much more specific criterion than intended. The actual economy efficiency is determined after the introduction into the production of scientific products, the calculation is carried out according to the costs that went into practice for scientific research and introduction. In this, the real effect is often less than expected. It is considered the most reliable criterion for economic efficiency.

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